

Trace the Harsh and Hardships of the Women's Portrayal of Shashi's Short Stories

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Abstract

Deshpande's short stories show how all children learn certain misconceptions from their parents to imitate from them. The Indian culture makes the girls alien to their own maternal home after their marriage. Right from the beginning they are brought up imbibing such thoughts in their mind. As a result they naturally feel themselves alien in their maternal home where a place where they have been born and brought up. Her the women characters are operative sensibility becomes an imposition only when the woman is laid rigid rules of how they should behave. But if the rules are rigidly laid for them, as a wife or a mother that she should do this furtherly, unhappiness and uneasiness dawns for a woman who finds herself ways to get ride of the suffocating relationships. Moreover the problems of women facing the infidelity of their husbands to go unnoticed. Unless the woman who faces the problem expresses that, no one can realize it.

His works reveals the operative sensibility of the women to examines their feelings of the Deshpande's women protagonists of all kind - married, unmarried, teenagers, children towards other relations to see how these roles react to each other. The chapter also examines the subjugated position of the women in Indian society and their positive reaffirmation. In some of her short stories Deshpande has portrayed the power of mothers and grandparents over their daughters and granddaughters. some other stories, the mothers are portrayed as isolated figures, by working within their limited purview. They are dominated by their men-folk, harassed by their in-laws and misunderstood by their daughters. If Jaya of "It was the Nightingale" is the guilty of going ahead with her career neglecting her family life, Hema of "A Wall is Safer" is the guilty of giving importance to the family by sacrificing her career.

Since all it goes ill-informed the victims endure it by all themselves as in "Travel Plans" and "A Day like Any Other" which reveal the psychological turmoil of a wife whose husband has turned unfaithful to her.

The anguish of women being cheated by the men forms one of the major concerns of Deshpande's short stories. The problem of unwanted pregnancy is dealt in the "Death of a Child", and the rape of the protagonist's daughter and its consequent pregnancy in "It was

Dark". "It Was Dark" is about a 14 year old girl, who gets pregnant for being innocent to trust all the male family members. Her pain is intolerable and her life becomes totally a devoid of all light and joy. The Marital rape is the problem of the protagonist in "The Intrusion". She talks about the husband's intrusion into the wife's physical and psychological privacy. Deshpande also talks of the mother not willing to have the third child in the "Death of a Child" the working woman going to abroad in the pursuit of her career in "It Was The Nightingale", a widow getting ready for the remarriage in "The Cruelty Game" and so on.

Deshpande's central focus is on the gender equality as all her writings strive to suggest a small or right changes required for the welfare of not only a women but also men. Her desire is to transform the modification which is wished in her works. In every short story, she tries to show how the women characters are in the clutches of patriarchy in one or another way, but each one of them tries to break free from the patriarchal shackles. The women characters are gleaming as the protagonists in her stories.

It has scrutinized a handful of her stories to show how the women characters ultimately emerge as being independent and powerful. All the characters of Shashi Deshpande's stories are individuals who belong to the common folk. They are pretty and identifiable, to undergo identifiable situations. The special thing to note in her writings that she remains at the grass root level, for elevating her characters to experience through their actions for pleasurable experience. Almost all the stories of the protagonists have broken the stereotyped and the traditional image of the women, may it be in the case of the wife who is not ready to submit to her husband's wish to have the third child in the "Death of a Child", and the working woman going to abroad in pursuit of her career in the "It Was The Nightingale", Shaku in divorcing her husband" the old woman in favour of the divorcee in the "And Then?", a widow getting ready for remarriage in "The Cruelty Game" and so on. But they hardly go out of the traditional to mould the institution of the marriage.

Shashi Deshpande has beautifully analysed the narrative techniques and stylistic devices adopted by in her select short stories. This chapter also explores how her writing style aids in dealing with the concept such as the man-woman relationship, to operate sensibility of the women and the New Women. Many of her stories, Deshpande has employed the flash back technique with the narrative going back and forth in time. As a result the narrator describes the events with in the hindsight.

Deshpande criticizes the Indian parents' perception for regarding the marriage as the sole purpose of a woman's existence. A girl gets ready to become the wife of the man who has made a mould ready for his wife. The writer depicts the humiliation of a girl's parent to undergo in the name of "bride viewing" ceremony - a custom in the Indian society where the groom's family visits the bride's family with an air of the importance, as if they are going to change the entire fate of the girl. She depicts how they humiliate the girl by asking several questions, to relish the snacks served and leave the house announcing that they will inform later without understanding the anxiety, and the eagerness of the bride's family. She portrays how the girl is made to stand in front of strangers while the father starts explaining her greatness, just as a salesman exhibits his products to the customers and how the self respect of the girl is trampled to pieces. Like a normal Indian girl, she considers the marriage is an essential thing in life. Hence she feels relieved on hearing that the groom's party has given their consent. Like any other average girl, she too has her own dreams about her husband – But practical, she understands her father's worries and accepts the situation. Deshpande shows how the women suffer due to the ruthless behaviour of the men who marries them for the sake of their parents without considering the plight of women. Such men in many cases abandon their wives.

Her short stories has used 'the dark', 'the sun light', 'death' and 'life' and 'silence' as the metaphors. The metaphor of 'silence' is used in the short story, "Can You Hear Silence?" In the

story "Rain" the protagonist talks of 'rain' as 'death' and 'desolation' as 'sorrow'. Similarly the metaphor of death is used in this story "Death of a Child". In all these stories metaphors are continuously discussed in one way or another, they are very closely interlinked to the main theme. The image of the confining 'wall' illustrates her plight; and the wall not only conceals the outer horizon from her sight but also traps her within itself, thus doubly annihilating her identity. In some stories such as "A Day Like Any Other", Deshpande makes the reader to get confused as whom "her" refers to - whether the protagonist of the story or her friend since the words "she" and "her" are simultaneously used for the protagonist and her friend. In spite of such ambiguities, Deshpande's style of writing has elevated her as one of the major Indian English short story writer.

In short, Deshpande has portrayed the new Indian woman her dilemmas, and efforts to understand herself to preserve her identity as the wife, mother and, above all, as a human being in the tradition-bound, in male-dominated the Indian society. The Indian woman's plight is a part of the general human predicament, through her experience is significantly more intense. As a sensible the woman writer, she likes to be read as the human being and not as a surrogate for others.

In one of her stories, Deshpande highlights the issue of a rape and its consequences. She clearly depicts the agony of the parents of a raped girl and their reaction towards the child. It is the mother who tries to understand the girl to bring her back to normalcy whereas the father behaves as if he were stranger to the girl. The author even tries to bring the light of vulnerable feelings of the women after their marriage. When they are asked to submit themselves to their husband thus breaking the wall they have built around themselves. She has also portrayed the mother who feels that her daughter should not face the humiliation and vulnerability, which she felt on the day of her marriage. She does not want her daughter to be overshadowed by the traditions. Hence she has allowed her to grow up as a modern girl without any inhibitions. The story presents the condition of the women who are at crossroads level between the tradition and the modernity.

Deshpande's feminism is an essential for the Indian in the sense that is born out of the predicament of the Indian women contradictory to their identities: as the tradition and modernity, family and profession, and culture and nature. The emotional turmoil suffered by the complicated Western educated their Indian Women caught in between the tradition and the modernity is liable to the literary analysis from a feministic perspective. Her feminism is humanistic in its outlook. Shashi Deshpande's fiction should be valued against the background of the Indian culture and the tradition to be judged against the scales of the Western feminist literature.

It is interesting to unveil the images of the women in Indian literature when put together, the picture in its totality makes for the fascinating reading. The Women in India are still caught in between the feudal values and the fast approaching of new life. Shuttling between the burden of home workplace, child bearing, mothering, and struggling with the conventions, The women should first to survive the question of the equality arises afterwards. She attempts to intimately analyze men and the woman relationships within the ambit of their family and the society usually they concentrate on the experiences to gain in life, by recalling yet another instance of the Jane Austen with her narrow range of the limited knowledge.

In This paper her protagonists are the modern, educated, and the Indian women torn in between the traditional ideas and their intellect. Though they never cross the threshold of their family to walk away from the accepted roles of as a wife and a mother, by revolting in their own way. She argues that women never fight for the unwanted rights but for their dignity and also for the freedom with in adjustable family environment. This is what she has tried to convey through her writing by projecting the different types of the protagonists in all her stories.

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